

The Implementation of Omnichannel Marketing to Improve Customer Engagement and Customer Retention in English Courses

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ABSTRACT: English is one of the most spoken languages in the world, and understanding the language opens a gateway to connecting with other cultures and unlocking a vast source of information from around the world. In Indonesia, one of the oldest and most prominent English course institutions known as LIA is recently struggling to retain a stable amount of students. Based on data provided by the institution, one of its branches experienced a decline from 1200 students to just 300.

The purpose of this research is to study the impact of customer experience and omnichannel marketing on customer switching behavior. This research utilizes a quantitative approach and purposive sampling of 234 respondents from active LIA students in Greater Jakarta, including its neighboring cities such as Bekasi, Tangerang, and Depok. The hypothesis was tested using multiple linear regression. The result of this study indicates that customer expectation and omnichannel marketing have a significant and positive impact on the switching behavior of LIA students. Findings from this study were useful for future research regarding these fields of study and the topics while also providing practical implementation of omnichannel marketing in the forms of social media advertising, search engine optimization, sales promotion, and conventional word-of-mouth marketing to attract potential customers and mitigate the switching behavior.

KEYWORDS: Customer Experience, Omnichannel Marketing, Switching Behavior, English Course, Social Media Advertising, Search Engine Optimization, Sales Promotion, Conventional Word of Mouth

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

English is often regarded as one of the most important languages in the world, allowing people from several nations to interact and share their knowledge. Unlike in neighboring Singapore, Malaysia, and Hong Kong, English is less often spoken on a daily basis in Indonesia; it is more likely to be taught and studied academically rather than spoken in informal conversational exchanges. English communication will most likely occur in classes, competitions, organizational activities, and other academic situations for students. Mastering English will help students thrive in their education. The most prevalent issue that students encounter is communicating in English. The majority of graduates are not "industry ready" due to a lack of communication skills (Thanky, 2012).

The importance of English as a language is perhaps well known by the people of Indonesia, however, the level of English proficiency that every individual might aim for might differ depending on their needs, some of their needs might be satisfied just by learning English from watching movies or through exposure from international media and entertainment. Some might need a higher level of proficiency if they have a specific purpose such as entering a university or requiring a promotion. Several English proficiency tests have international recognition to measure the proficiency of individuals such as their grammar, listening skills, and vocabulary. These tests are known as TOEFL, TOEIC, IELTS, GEPT, and IBT. Each of these tests has its specific purposes, for example, TOEIC is more workplace oriented whereas IELTS and TOEFL are more designed specifically for academic purposes. For university students, these test scores serve as relevant evidence of English language proficiency that effectively benchmarks the graduates for professional workplace communications (Hsu, 2010).

One institution that had served the general public of Indonesia as an English language course provider for many years is LIA. The institution was established in 1959 with only 19 students, over the years the institution has provided English academic services for students, teachers, and the general public. They are one of the most well-recognized brands and have a long history of collaborations with companies, government institutions, and universities. LIA was once the first establishment in people's minds when they were looking to enroll in an English course as it is one of the best places to learn English properly. LIA's vision is to provide a learning

institution that serves as the best and most widespread learning center in Indonesia, LIA is committed to developing students into top-notch human capital.

1.2 Problem Exploration & Research Questions

Recently, the number of students registering for the course has been steadily decreasing over each term's registration period. The firm is encountering marketing issues in retaining more students than it has in the past. When students are taking courses, they will recommend their friends to join the courses, and their parents will also be involved in this word-of-mouth strategy. The company frequently offers incentives to students who invited their friends to enter, usually in the form of discounts or free merchandise given for every term directly. The organization has previously demonstrated efforts to perform digital marketing; nonetheless, interaction is fairly poor, and their students usually apply offline by visiting the facility.

These days, LIA as an institution is struggling to maintain the number of students in their branches, most of them are in a state of decline, and some are worse than others. they see a reduction from 1200 students in a term to just 300, even though some branches are combining their classes with other branches and converting them into solely online classes to reduce costs as some classes only have less than 10 students. aside from onsite classes, they also have difficulties gaining the attractiveness of their tests. The price to take a course in LIA is more affordable than what the competitor charge. However, the price might not necessarily be the reason why students prefer other institutions to LIA. Previously, their English Proficiency Tests (EPT) have been acknowledged by renowned institutions and multinational companies. entrants and applicants are required to take.

The main objective of conducting this research is to better understand customer switching behavior and the customer expectations of English course students. In order to successfully implement omnichannel marketing to gain more customers and increase the customer retention rate in LIA, it is necessary to understand the circumstances from the customer's point of view. Obtaining information as to what the customers are really interested in when they are signing to a course would be beneficial in adjusting the academic system to suit the customer's expectations.

Researchers will be able to establish their study aims, evaluate information needs, and select appropriate research designs if they have well-defined research questions. As a result, the following are the study's developed research questions:

1. Does customer expectation have a significant relationship with the customer switching behavior of students taking an English course at LIA?
2. Does the implementation of omnichannel marketing have a significant relationship with the customer switching behavior of students taking an English course at LIA?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Customer Expectation

The sources of customer expectation are derived from the information gained by the customer regarding the upcoming service encounter with a particular business, the company conducts these information communications. (Gures et al., 2014) Customer expectations can be defined as the personal standards set by the customers to assess the quality of a service experience they are provided with. three hierarchical levels can determine the level of expectation by the customer: base expectations, specifications and requirements, and pleasure or delight which are also known as implicit expectations, explicit expectations, and hidden expectations (Tukiran et al., 2021). based on these levels, a business can set its standards of service to satisfy its customer's expectations in order to gain customer satisfaction customers characterized benchmarks referred to as customer expectations to evaluate the quality of a service experience (Tukiran et al., 2021).

H1. Customer Expectations have a significant positive relationship with the Switching Behavior of LIA Students

2.2 Omnichannel Marketing

Exceeding multichannel marketing by implementing cooperation across numerous distribution channels to provide a unified consumer experience (Shankar & Kushwaha, 2021). Online and offline marketing communication channels operate concurrently in omnichannel marketing rather than in parallel in multichannel marketing (Piotrowicz & Cuthbertson, 2018). The continuous rise in e-commerce and digital marketing trends has resulted in the creation of omnichannel marketing strategies. At the moment, clients may search and buy using both online and physical channels. Customers may experience items and services before purchasing them through marketing channels online with omnichannel marketing.

Customers are provided omnichannel promotions across different channels during their purchase process (Blom et al., 2021). As a result, boosting the weight of the information offered is critical for impressing clients via the offline channel (Dzyabura et al., 2019). However, it is equally critical to verify that the information provided to clients in both channels is consistent. The disparity in information between online and physical channels may influence a customer's appraisal of a product, resulting in a shift in the customer's product preferences (Dzyabura et al., 2019). Because of the availability of omnichannel shopping, consumers' spending and product variety have expanded, as have transaction costs, service quality, and brand image (Luo et al., 2020).

Omnichannel marketing management coordinates the operation of several marketing channels and consumer touchpoints in order to create the best possible customer experience and performance across channels (Verhoef et al., 2015). Omnichannel marketing involves the management of both online and offline information dissemination channels. An omnichannel approach is built on communication.

H2. Omnichannel Marketing has a significant positive relationship with the Switching Behavior of LIA students

2.3 Switching Behavior

Consumer switching behavior refers to the process through which customers consider allocating resources such as time, effort, and money to obtain a variety of items and services from multiple suppliers (Garga et al., 2019). Customer switching behavior is defined as the conduct of consumers retracting and terminating their relationship with a business, which symbolizes the customer's decision to discontinue purchasing items or services given by a certain organization (Zikiene & Pileliene, 2016).

Client switching behavior is the process by which a customer abandons their allegiance to their current service provider and switches to another provider owing to discontent or any other issues that may have arisen (Shah et al., 2018). References from family members may be factors that encourage customers to acquire habits to switch brands since family members create an environment for individuals to gain values and grow and form their personalities. Families are capable of forming first views of a brand, which may develop into a habit that they follow for the rest of their lives (Garga et al., 2019).

Consumers who have the option to seek out multiple providers may switch from one brand to another. Consumers will seek out suppliers that best meet their demands, whether it's in terms of service quality, pricing, or product quality. Customer switching behavior has an effect on customers who are loyal to a brand. If a customer's demands are not met by one brand, he or she will switch to another (Satish et al., 2014).

2.4 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of this research is developed based on the business issue formulated earlier in the first chapter of this research. The business issue of LIA is the lack of customer retention and the lack of engagement in the current marketing methods conducted by LIA to gain new customers and maintain current customers to finish their courses.

This conceptual framework will be used as a platform to formulate a strategy to be used to implement omnichannel marketing to improve the current marketing strategy that is being conducted by LIA. The concept of omnichannel marketing is relatively new to the company and the English course service industry. Therefore, it requires more effort to implement omnichannel marketing.

The components of omnichannel marketing implemented in this research conceptual framework are as follows. Social media advertising is interactive and considered a modern technology, social media advertising represents the most advanced form of the business-to-customer communication channel (Alalwan, 2018). Social media advertising and related social media engagement are the collections of experiences that each individual obtains while interacting with social media advertising on the platform (Voorveld et al., 2018). search engine optimization (SEO) known as the process of persuading search engines to provide users with recommendations based on the advertiser's content (Panchal et al., 2021). Word of mouth is a well-established concept where a person shares his views with another person. The views shared by the person can contain references for products or services that the person has previously received. The studies in consumer behavior suggest that words of mouth have a strong influence on the psychology of the person (Lo, 2012). Sales promotion is an action-focused marketing strategy that has a direct impact on the behavior of the business's customers. However, if the customer takes no action to take advantage during the specified period of the sales promotion, they will not gain any benefit (Blattberg & Briesch, 2012).

Figure 1. Proposed Research Framework

The model is constructed to design the implementation of omnichannel marketing towards LIA’s marketing strategy. Through the implementation of omnichannel marketing, LIA should be able to effectively communicate information regarding the services and promotions LIA currently provides to its customers through online and offline channels seamlessly. Therefore, directing the customer’s expectation to better understand the company itself and its business in education, hopefully mitigating the impact of customer switching behavior and maintaining customer retention in the institution.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection

The Population is described in research terminology as a complete collection of individuals, institutions, communities, organizations, items, and so on that have similar traits that are of interest to a researcher. To be able to establish the population size and location that will be included in this research, the research population must be clearly defined and concentrated. The total population targets LIA students that are currently enrolled in classes of LIA Pramuka.

The data sources that will be used in this research will be gathered from primary sources and secondary sources as the following.

Primary sources

Primary data is information created or acquired by researchers expressly for the study project at hand and gained through survey and observation methods (Malhotra, 2007). Primary data has consisted of data collected from first-hand sources, therefore the surveys answered by the population sample will be the source of primary data for this research. The survey will be conducted in LIA and gathers data from active LIA students, the target will be a minimum of 200 survey respondents.

This study uses multiple-choice questions. The survey will be separated into two sections. Demographic questions and numerous questions on a 5-point Likert scale. Age range, course level, respondent’s domicile, active social media platform, and their first awareness of LIA are included in the demographic section.

The Likert scale is a common scale that asks respondents to rate their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements about the stimuli. The Likert scale is included in the interval scale in data processing; the determination of the Likert scale in this

study is conducted on a scale of 1 to 5. All factors are measured using the 5-point Likert scale, which means that if an answer has a low weight, a score of 1 (one) is assigned. And so on, until a score of 5 (five) is assigned if the response has a high weight. The range of the 5-point Likert scale in this research is as follows:

Table 1. 5-Point Likert Scale

Value	Categorization
1	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neutral
4	Agree
5	Strongly Agree

Secondary sources

Secondary data sources are the data gathered from other sources that are readily available before the research is conducted. The secondary sources that will be used in this research are obtained from literature, scientific journals, previous related studies and research, and also company data gathered from LIA's Website, Staff Input, and documents that the company granted access to the author.

3.2 Sampling Method

In research terms, the Population is defined as a comprehensive collection of individuals, institutions, communities, organizations, items, and so on that have similar traits that are of interest to a researcher. To be able to identify the population size and location that will be included in this research, the research population must be precisely defined and concentrated. The demographic of respondents in this study consists of people who have applied and enrolled at LIA and are currently studying in LIA Pramuka, the target will be a minimum of 200 survey respondents (Malhotra, 2007).

A research sample is a subset of the population chosen for its degree of representation. The sampling strategy utilized in this research is purposive sampling. The scope of the research samples is to be as follows:

1. Students currently enrolled in LIA Courses in LIA Pramuka online and offline classes.
2. Students under 18 years of age who studies at LIA and is currently in their academic years, and students above 25-35 years of age who studies at LIA and is currently in their professional career.
3. Students residing in Greater Jakarta and the Jabodetabek Area.

3.3 Research Design

This study employs a survey technique that determines a sample in order to generalize the population. This study describes the impact on the model's hypothesized variables based on the degree of explanation. The existing variables of this research are Omnichannel Marketing, Customer Expectation, Customer Switching Behavior, and Customer Retention. A descriptive study is a form of conclusive study in which the primary goal is to describe something, such as market features or functions. The descriptive research design used in this study is a cross-sectional design. Cross-sectional research collects information from the population sample just once. A questionnaire survey for the pretest was issued to the respondents in order to obtain information from the sample. This study utilizes a quantitative technique. Quantitative research, according to Minichiello & Kottler (2010), is focused on uncovering facts about social processes while assuming a fixed and measurable reality. For example, he argued that the methodological approach to getting quantitative data is through examining numerical comparisons and statistical judgments.

3.4 Reliability Test - Cronbach's Alpha

The degree to which your data collection procedures or analysis procedures produce consistent results is referred to as reliability (Saunders et al., 2016). Cronbach's alpha is the most frequently used internal consistency metric. Internal consistency reliability is

a measure of reliability that assesses how well various test items exploring the same concept generate consistent findings. It is most typically used when many Likert questions create a scale in a survey or questionnaire and you want to know if the scale is dependable. The degree to which a survey questionnaire delivers consistent and steady findings is referred to as its reliability.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha Description

Cronbach's Alpha	Description
0.93-0.94	Excellent
0.91-0.93	Strong
0.85-0.90	Reliable
0.81-0.84	Robust
0.50-0.80	Moderate
Less than 0.50	Low

Source: ((Tan, 2009),(Taber, 2017))

If the instrument's reliability is high, the inaccuracies in the data obtained are minimal, and the data's accuracy and reliability are high. Cronbach's alpha is used to assess the dependability of this research instrument.

3.5 Validity Test

Validity is determined by the relevant and proper interpretation of the data produced from the measuring instrument as an outcome of the analysis (SÜRÜCÜ & MASLAKÇI, 2020). If a research instrument can be measured or valued, it is said to be valid. A valid instrument can provide data from various studies. Validity is the degree to which the outcomes are genuine and credible.

3.6 Normality Test

Conducting a normality test will indicate whether or not the independent variables in the linear regression are regularly distributed. According to Green and Salkind (2014), The criteria of normally distributed data in conducting a normality test is that the P-Value exceeds 0.05. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test is the most often used normality test. If the p-value is equal to or exceeds 0.05 the results will indicate that the data is normally distributed.

3.7 Data Analysis Method - Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regression is a statistical method for analyzing the relationship between a scalar response (or dependent variable) and one or more explanatory factors (or independent variables). Simple linear regression refers to the circumstance where there is just one dependent variable. In multiple linear regression, the model is extended to include more than one explanatory variable (Tranmer et al., 2008).

The purpose of regression analysis is to establish the possibility of introducing fluctuations in the independent variable can explain changes in the dependent variable to a certain degree, utilizing a linear connection between the dependent variable and one or more independent variables.

3.8 Hypothesis Test

The hypothesis was tested using an analysis with a 5% error margin. As a result, the t-value chosen is 1.96. Because all of the hypotheses expected a positive effect, a hypothesis is accepted if the t-value is more than 1.96 and rejected if the t-value is less than 1.96. The table below displays the t-values and whether or not the hypothesis is accepted (Hair, 2019).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Analysis Results

Table 3. Descriptive Analysis Results

Variable	Number of Samples	Minimum	Maximum	Total Mean
Customer Expectation	234	29	75	59.9
Omnichannel Marketing	234	27	60	49.5
Switching Behavior	234	50	105	79.9

Source: SPSS Output conducted by the Researcher

From the table above it can be concluded that the mean score for customer expectation is 59.9 out of a minimum of 29 and maximum of 75 which indicates that the majority of respondents agree to the statement of the surveys regarding the attributes of the variable customer expectation towards LIA, for omnichannel marketing the score is 49.5 out of a maximum of 60 which means that the majority of respondents are showing a positive feeling with the statements regarding omnichannel marketing from the survey. Lastly, for switching behavior the respondents are also agreeing with the statements where the mean is 79.9 out of a minimum of 50 and a maximum of 105.

4.2 Respondent’s Profile

Respondents which are LIA students are categorized based on their age, course levels, domicile, favorite social media platform, their experience taking English courses at other institutions, and also their first introduction to LIA.

Table 4. Respondent’s Profile

Category	Results
Age	70.1% of the respondents are under 18 years old
Course Level	53.8% of the respondents are in the English for adults program which is for high school students, followed by English for teens with 18.4% which are for junior high school students
Domicile	44% of the respondents are residing in East Jakarta, 20.1% are residing in Central Jakarta, 13.7% are residing in South Jakarta, 14.5% are residing in Bekasi, 4.3% are residing in Depok and the minority of 2.6% are residing in West Jakarta
Active Social Media Platform	The most preferred social media platform is Instagram 35.4%, followed by Youtube 23.7% and Tiktok 22.9%
Experience with other Institutions	67.8% of Respondents have never tried taking an English course at other institutions, and 32.2% have tried taking a course at other institutions

First Introduction	The majority (88.9%) of the respondents are first introduced to LIA through a reference from their relatives, Social media advertisements accounts for 6%, followed by brochures 3.4% and banner advertisements at 1.7%.
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Source: Survey Results Conducted by the Author

4.3 Pre-Test Reliability Test

Reliability test is conducted to measure the reliability of each construct, the Cronbach’s alpha coefficient will be used, The higher the score of the Cronbach’s Alpha, the consistency of the construct is also higher. according to Taber (2017), a Cronbach’s Alpha value of above 0.81 is considered robust.

Table 5. Reliability Test Results

Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha	N of Items
Switching Behavior	0.866	21
Customer Expectation	0.948	15
Omnichannel Marketing	0.928	12

Source: SPSS Test Output by the Author

Based on the results of the reliability test using SPSS it can be concluded that all of the variables in this research’s constructs achieved a Cronbach’s Alpha value of greater than 0.81. Switching Behavior has a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.866 considered Robust, Customer Expectation has a Cronbach’s Alpha of 0.948 which is considered Excellent, and Omnichannel Marketing has a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.928 considered Strong (Taber, 2017).

4.4 Pre-Test Validity Test

To measure the validity of the research instrument, validity test is conducted as a pre-test. Pearson Correlation is used to verify the questionnaire's validity. The validity test Pearson correlation is performed by correlating each questionnaire item. The table above demonstrates the data's validity by examining the coefficient correlation. If the value of the Pearson rank coefficient correlation is between 0.30 and 1.0, it may be characterized as moderate to extremely strong. In this investigation, Testing the The validity of measuring equipment is determined by assessing the correlation between item scores. from each area, with a total score from all aspects Pearson's Correlation is one of the formulae used to assess the validity.

Table 6. Validity Test Results

Variables	Indicators	Coefficient Pearson’s Correlation of Average Variables	P-Value (Sig.)	N of Items
Switching Behavior	SB1	0.528	0.000	234
	SB2	0.622	0.000	234
	SB3	0.588	0.000	234
	SB4	0.551	0.000	234

Variables	Indicators	Coefficient Pearson's Correlation of Average Variables	P-Value (Sig.)	N of Items	
	SB5	0.607	0.000	234	
	SB6	0.654	0.000	234	
	SB7	0.635	0.000	234	
	SB8	0.661	0.000	234	
	SB9	0.704	0.000	234	
	SB10	0.482	0.000	234	
	SB11	0.489	0.000	234	
	SB12	0.558	0.000	234	
	SB13	0.068	0.297	234	
	SB14	0.472	0.000	234	
	SB15	0.635	0.000	234	
	SB16	0.367	0.000	234	
	SB17	0.338	0.000	234	
	SB18	0.359	0.000	234	
	SB19	0.439	0.000	234	
	SB20	0.491	0.000	234	
	SB21	0.555	0.000	234	
	Customer Expectation	CE1	0.608	0.000	234
		CE2	0.784	0.000	234
		CE3	0.623	0.000	234
		CE4	0.701	0.000	234
CE5		0.695	0.000	234	
CE6		0.676	0.000	234	
CE7		0.751	0.000	234	
CE8		0.728	0.000	234	

Variables	Indicators	Coefficient Pearson's Correlation of Average Variables	P-Value (Sig.)	N of Items
	CE9	0.715	0.000	234
	CE10	0.744	0.000	234
	CE11	0.760	0.000	234
	CE12	0.738	0.000	234
	CE13	0.638	0.000	234
	CE14	0.651	0.000	234
	CE15	0.702	0.000	234
Omnichannel Marketing	OM1	0.661	0.000	234
	OM2	0.691	0.000	234
	OM3	0.666	0.000	234
	OM4	0.664	0.000	234
	OM5	0.691	0.000	234
	OM6	0.622	0.000	234
	OM7	0.722	0.000	234
	OM8	0.628	0.000	234
	OM9	0.738	0.000	234
	OM10	0.800	0.000	234
	OM11	0.545	0.000	234
	OM12	0.635	0.000	234

Source: SPSS Test Output by the Author

The measure of each variable of each research is listed in the table above, it can be seen that a variable in Switching Behavior of SB13 does not meet the requirements to be considered as valid, it has an unsatisfactory score of Pearson's Correlation of 0.068 and a P-Value of 0.297, Therefore, variable SB13 will not be used

4.5 Normality Testing

Normality tests are used in complement to the graphical assessment of normality. Kurtosis tests include the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test, the Lilliefors corrected K-S test, the Shapiro-Wilk test, the Anderson-Darling test, the Cramer-von Mises test, the D'Agostino skewness test, the Anscombe-Glynn kurtosis test, the D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus test, and The K-S test is one of them, and both the K-S and Shapiro-Wilk tests can be done simultaneously. The aforementioned tests listed above compare the sample scores to a normally distributed set of scores with the same mean and standard deviation (Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012).

Table 7. Kolmogorov Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		Unstandardized Residual
N		234
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	7.15084180
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.040
	Positive	.032
	Negative	-.040
Test Statistic		.040
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
- b. Calculated from data.
- c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
- d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

The normality test result is presented in the following table above, with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (Sig) or P-Value of .200 which exceeds the criteria of 0.05 indicating that the data is normally distributed.

4.6 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression is a technique for defining a linear connection between numerous independent variables and a dependent variable. Multiple linear regression was employed in this study to assess the strength of the linear connection between variables of Customer Expectation, Omnichannel Marketing, and Switching Behavior.

4.6.1 Correlation Analysis

Table 8. Correlation Between Variables

		Switching Behavior	Customer Expectation	Omnichannel Marketing
Switching Behavior	Pearson Correlation	1	.725**	.712**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	234	234	234
Customer Expectation	Pearson Correlation	.725**	1	.762**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	234	234	234
Omnichannel Marketing	Pearson Correlation	.712**	.762**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	234	234	234

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Test Output by the Author

According to the correlation Table above, the relationship associations between the variables are statistically significant (less than 0.05), and all of the independent variables have a strong correlation with the dependent variables. Switching behavior has a strong relationship with Customer Expectation with a Pearson correlation of 0.73, and also Switching Behavior with Omnichannel marketing has a Pearson correlation of 0.71

4.6.2 Coefficients (β) Results

Table 9. Coefficients (β) Results

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	26.180	3.020		8.669	.000
	Customer Expectation	.469	.070	.435	6.663	.000
	Omnichannel Marketing	.519	.089	.380	5.824	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Switching Behavior

Source: SPSS Test Output by the Author

A coefficient table is another useful tool for explaining the relationship between two variables. according to the significance (Sig.) column in the preceding table, The p-value for each independent variable is less than 0.05, This shown that Customer Expectation and Omnichannel Marketing had a significant influence on LIA's Customers' Switching Behavior.

4.6.3 Model Feasibility Test (F-Test)

Table 10. F-Test Results

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16900.546	2	8450.273	163.837	.000 ^b
	Residual	11914.347	231	51.577		
	Total	28814.893	233			

a. Dependent Variable: Switching Behavior

b. Predictors: (Constant), Omnichannel Marketing, Customer Expectation

Source: SPSS Test Output by the Author

The above model feasibility test, often referred to as the F - test examines whether the overall independent factors have a model feasibility impact on the dependent variable. The F - test criteria state that if the significant value of the result is less than 0.05, the independent variable has a simultaneous influence on the dependent variable. The (Sig) Value in the table above is 0.000. The results of the test indicate that Omnichannel Marketing and Customer Expectation has a simultaneous effect on Switching Behavior.

4.6.4 Model Summary

Table 11. Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.766 ^a	.587	.583	7.18173

a. Predictors: (Constant), Omnichannel Marketing, Customer Expectation

Source: SPSS Test Output by the Author

The multiple correlation coefficient R has a value of 0.766, based on the summary of multiple regressions in the table above. Considering R is positive, there exists a positive linear relationship between Omnichannel Marketing, Customer Expectation, and Customer Switching Behavior. The R Square (R^2) for this study model is 0.587, indicating that the data is more than 0.5 and closer to 1. This means that 58.7% of the factors in Omnichannel Marketing and Customer Expectation may significantly explain customer switching behavior in LIA.

4.7 Hypotheses Testing

The main purpose of conducting T-Value and P-Value analysis is to analyze the impact and significance of each independent variable towards the dependent variable, which in this research is the Customer Expectation towards Switching Behavior as the first hypothesis and Omnichannel Marketing towards Switching Behavior as the second hypothesis. In this research, both hypotheses are accepted as their P-Values are both 0.000 which is lower than 0.05. The criteria of the analysis are that the hypothesis is accepted if the P-Value is less than 0.05. If the hypothesis's P-value is more than 0.05, it is rejected (George & Mallery, 2019).

Figure 1. Path Diagram of Hypotheses testing of the Research Framework

The T-value may be used to determine if the observable variables have a significant influence on other observable variables in the study based on the results of the analysis. If the T-value for the hypothesis that predicts a positive impact is 1.96, it may be determined that the connection between the latent variables is significant, and the hypothesis can be accepted. It can be concluded that both hypotheses of this research can be accepted as the t-values are both exceeding 1.96 therefore, both hypotheses between customer expectations towards switching behavior with a T-value of 6.663 and omnichannel marketing towards switching behavior with a T-value of 5.824 are accepted and also significant as they are above the 1.96 thresholds.

4.8 Implementation Plan for Omnichannel Marketing

LIA is one of the market leaders in the English course sector, The company was established in 1959 and has branches all across Indonesia. Many successful people have taken a course in LIA during their academic career. However, the business environment in the English education sector is changing and modernizing in recent years. Recently LIA has been weak in its marketing strategy to

penetrate the market further. The search engine marketing of LIA is unoptimized whereas their rivals are parasitizing their search engine results by using paid advertisements such as google ads and showing their advertisements first when potential customers are searching for the keywords related to LIA and their business which affects the whole company and all the branches, not just LIA Pramuka. Their social media advertising is facing challenges to reach more potential customers and engagement in their social media accounts is quite low. Each term in the education calendar of LIA courses are taking three months. At the beginning of each term, there are placement tests where new students are able to enroll at LIA to study the courses. Therefore, the implementation of these omnichannel marketing strategies listed below has to be in line with the beginning of each term. To conduct the implementation action plans, the schedule must follow the academic calendar of LIA, each quarter is in line with the corresponding three months terms that LIA is familiar with. At the beginning of the first term, LIA must develop its social media presence by registering a business account for the preferred social media which are Instagram, YouTube, and Tiktok. later in the same quarter, the institution can start its advertising campaign through the services each platform provides. While initializing their corporate social media profile, teachers and other staff could encourage students to participate in social media marketing activities by creating their own content. In addition to making their own content, there are many YouTube channels with different types of viewers that holds sponsorship potential to reach a broader audience through YouTube, This can be done at the end of every term or before the start of the following term as the advertisements would target audiences that are going to enroll in each course. Therefore the advertisements would reach them and by the time the content reaches them they are in time for the registration period for the following term.

After the social media advertisement phase is completed, LIA can shift its focus to search engine optimization. LIA should participate in the keyword auction and utilize search engine marketing to prioritize the results to their corporate website. Because search engines are working primarily as an intermediary to direct users and potential customers to their website, the corporate website itself has to provide useful information in an attractive manner. The website has to be continuously updated throughout the year to ensure that the most updated information regarding prices, schedules, programs, and activities is listed. The website should also integrate links to other social media profiles, phone numbers, and WhatsApp contact.

The referral code program should integrate with the implementation of omnichannel marketing as quickly as possible, in the beginning of the first term, the system has to be developed and tested, therefore the duration of the node takes a very long time through five months of development to ensure that the system is working properly. During those five months periods, there are trials and distributions to both students and influencers. The system for the referral codes has to take into account the usage limit, and the ability to assess the performance of the codes by how often the codes were used during the registration period. if the codes have exceeded a certain limit of usage, then the code cannot be used again and therefore it is also assessed that the holder of the code has reached and influenced a certain amount of customers.

Customers who use the code can also be assessed whether they are new students or they are already enrolled in the courses before by categorizing whether they are taking the placement tests or not, the size of the incentives that each batch of codes is given has to be able to be adjusted depending on the need to gain new customers or to retain customers and develop brand loyalty. To gain loyal customers, the referral code should provide larger benefits to customers who are already taking courses in LIA instead of new students. After determining whether the referral code has reached a certain amount of customers, the level of performance that conventional word-of-mouth advertising has reached can also be assessed through the referral code in an easier way, students whose referral code has reached more customers can be rewarded with bigger discounts to their courses. LIA has always given free courses to students who are outstanding at their level. At the end of each term, students who have the highest grades amongst their peers in the same level, not just the same class are able to continue to the next level for free. This same treatment could also be used for students whose referral codes have reached a certain amount of users. Therefore, also reduces the chance that students are making a deal amongst themselves to misuse the referral codes.

4.8.1 Social Media Advertising

Social media marketing and advertising foster viral interactions among consumers throughout virtual communities, forums, distributed content, fan pages, and promotion-related material published by companies on popular networking sites such as Twitter, Facebook, YouTube, Instagram, and others (Dwivedi et al., 2015). LIA has put an effort into establishing a presence on multiple social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube. However, the engagement by the customer and other users is quite low.

Based on the results of the survey, the most preferred social media platform by LIA students are Instagram, followed by YouTube and Tiktok. LIA has to focus its social media marketing efforts on these major platforms with the target to establish a strong presence and improve user engagement to gain more potential customers. LIA can collaborate with other content creators in order to attract the attention of the younger generation which is the specific target market for LIA's programs.

4.8.2 Search Engine Optimization

Currently one of LIA's most underutilized and underdeveloped marketing channel, rivals to the institution has used this opportunity to direct potential customers away from LIA and into their institution instead. The search engine results when customers are searching for LIA would show other institutions ahead of LIA's results. While using any search engine, users are given the choice to go between organic and sponsored links. The organic links are sorted according to their relevance to the keyword search, while the sponsored links are provided for advertisers to purchase through a competitive auction (Berman & Katona, 2013). Customers who are looking for English courses for the first time and who know LIA from other channels such as conventional word of mouth, and social media advertisements would recognize these other brands once they use their search engine to find LIA and discover other institutions offering the same services. If those competitors are offering services and promotions more suitable to the customer's needs, or other terms that are more to the customer's liking than what LIA can offer, those potential customers are more likely to enroll in other courses, rather than enrolling at LIA.

4.8.3 Sales Promotion

Sales promotions are most commonly used in a short period of time in the form of a price reduction to increase sales and the attractiveness of the product provided by a company. These promotional efforts would be limited to a few customers and are beneficial to both the company and the customers. Companies that conduct sales promotion gain more brand recognition, shifting customers away from their competitors and also increasing brand loyalty (DelVecchio et al., 2006).

Modernized sales promotion can be in the form of a referral code that is given to customers through digital content accessible through relevant posts, videos, short videos, and other content. These referral codes are used in a similar fashion to coupon codes that are found in magazines and newspapers, they provide a monetary benefit to the customer and also, and using different referral codes for different content creators and influencers would also assess the performance of each content creator and influencers in attracting customers.

4.8.4 Conventional Word of Mouth

One of LIA's strongest points in its marketing, from the survey it is known that 88.9% of the respondents knew LIA from references through their friends and relatives. Word of mouth allows customers to share their experiences in the form of information and opinion with other potential customers with the aim to direct both toward or away from the service or product provider (Jalilvand et al., 2011). Customers of LIA have the freedom to inform their relatives about both the good and the bad in the services that LIA provides. Most of them have the tendency to share the good experience they had as a form of their satisfaction with LIA's services. LIA students who have taken a course at LIA and felt an improvement in their English would excel in the subject at school and when their friends are curious about how they develop their English skills they will be referred to LIA. This chain of events is what LIA relied on for many years. These conventional words of mouth can be developed into referrals through social media content, mentions, and also collaborative efforts between more than one user in creating social media content.

5. CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

English is often regarded as one of the most useful languages in the world, allowing people from many places to communicate and exchange their ideas. English has been spoken less commonly in Indonesia than in adjacent countries like Singapore, Malaysia, and Hong Kong, and it is more likely to be taught and studied academically than applied in routine forms of communication. Making the larger population of Indonesia struggle to study English properly on their own.

The purpose of this research is to analyze the cause of the dwindling number of students across LIA's English courses and implement omnichannel marketing strategies as a way to mitigate the problem. Based on the findings acquired from the data analysis and survey with 234 respondents of LIA Pramuka students from the Greater Jakarta area that was conducted in the previous chapters of this research.

The majority of the respondents are under 18 years old which is in line with the majority of LIA students, The most populated level of the courses is from the English for adults level which is mostly filled with high school students. Most of the respondents prefer Instagram, Youtube, and Tiktok as their favored social media platforms, while the majority of the respondents have never taken a course from LIA's competitors, Lastly, conventional word of mouth has been the most effective way to promote LIA as the majority of respondents encountered LIA as a brand from references by their friends and relatives. From the analysis of the respondents, it can be concluded that Customer Expectation and Omnichannel Marketing have a significant and positive impact on Customer Switching Behavior.

In implementing omnichannel marketing, According to Piotrowicz & Cuthbertson (2018), both online and offline marketing communication channels are operating simultaneously. In the implementation of an omnichannel marketing strategy in LIA, Social Media Advertising, Search Engine Optimization, Sales Promotion and Conventional Word of Mouth are working seamlessly to promote LIA through the distribution of referral codes.

Referral codes can be distributed through social media by students, influencers, and sponsored YouTube channel content which can encourage their followers to apply for a course at LIA. This referral code can provide different levels of discounts depending on the users of the code. Referral codes can also be beneficial for marketers as their usage can be associated with the performance of the distributors, the more they are used, the better the performance of the promotor.

5.2 Limitations of The Research

Due to several constraints, the results of this research have some limitations, which are the following:

1. As a result of the sample being LIA Pramuka students, There was relatively little variance in the demographic profile of the respondents, such as the vast majority of respondents being under the age of 18. As a result of the majority of responders being in the same age bracket, the ideas and opinions expressed may be too similar.
2. Due to the time and resource constraints from both the researchers and the institution, the channels of marketing in omnichannel marketing are limited to social media advertising, search engine optimization, sales promotion, and conventional word-of-mouth marketing

5.3 Recommendations for Future Research

With additional resources, time, and dedication for future research, further improvement can be implemented to gain a better point of view regarding the related topics of omnichannel marketing in English course institutions. The following are the recommendations to be considered.

1. Inclusion of More Channels

This recommendation can be implemented for future research from LIA or by other independent researchers. To improve the effectiveness of Omnichannel Marketing, Similar institutions can implement more channels in their strategy such as using e-commerce platforms to conduct payment and promotion strategies and also implementing e-wallet payment to enable cashless transactions and payment schemes to attract more students. In these channels, referral codes can be in the form of promo codes and their usage is much more well-established than creating a new system from scratch.

2. Analyzing External Respondents

Further research in the future can be conducted by analyzing the general public's perception of the need of studying English from different backgrounds, professionally and academically. Therefore, it can be assessed whether the demand for English courses is still as high as in past years

3. Analyzing the need for Influencers

Any prominent Social Media figure with a significant number of followers who has a strong sense and expertise on the subject is promoting with the ability to monetize their image can be defined as a social media influencer (Jin et al., 2019). Social media influencers can also be recognized as micro-celebrities due to their relatively high prominence amongst their followers, which they employ for social impact and profit. In Indonesia, there are several influencers that can be suitable to promote English courses. They can be directly relevant to English courses or relevant to any industry that the institution is trying to promote.

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